

THE CONCEPT OF INFORMATION COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS IN THE CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382859>

Abstract. *Based on today's requirements, the credit-module system introduced in higher education institutions, opinions about the concept of information competence in students and the importance of its existence in this system, based on some theoretical data, analytical opinions are presented.*

Keywords: *credit-module system, students, information competence, competence, competence-based approach, European education system, educational trends.*

Today's modern educational requirements require its participants to have information competence. Therefore, at the same time, in the field of higher education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the issues of the credit-module system and the concept of information competence of students are relevant.

It is known that Europe introduced the credit-module system to make the education system more attractive. Today, this system is firmly taking its place in the education sector of many countries. The current education system in our country is no exception. In connection with the introduction of the credit module in education, a number of goals and tasks of education have expanded. This was also reflected in the reform of curricula and standards in higher education systems.

The goal of the credit-module system is related to the global educational trends and is related to the educational result expressed in the training of a highly qualified specialist with developed basic competencies, including information and information competence. Therefore, the sub-goal of the educational process of the higher education institution based on the credit-module system is the formation of the quality of the integrated personality of the learners, their successful integration into the information space and their self-awareness in professional activity and socio-economic reality based on information competence. is to provide.

One of the most discussed and relevant topics in higher education is the problem of competence development and assessment. If the understanding of the new concept of competence-based higher education and informing the participants of education coincides with the emergence of new state education standards, then the relevance of the issues of competence formation and assessment will increase even more.

It is known that, as a result of the acceleration of today's globalization processes, the process of informatization of society has had its impact on all spheres of life, and therefore, at present, human activity is increasingly flowing from the sphere of creation of material wealth to the sphere of information processing. At the same time, it is important to have information competence along with high-quality professional training to work in the information environment, which is a decisive factor for the successful development of economy, technology, science, politics and society as a whole. For this reason, the existence of the concept of information competence among students in the credit-module system established in higher education institutions based on

the demand of the time, in turn, determines the objective need for the modernization of state education.

We know that currently there is no single approach to defining the essence of the concept of "competence". In addition to this concept, the concepts of "basic competencies" and "professional competence" are used, and their uniqueness, differences, and components are considered and studied as one of the central subjects of educational theory today. This issue is mainly considered and studied by experts in the field of psychology and pedagogy as a deep research. B.S. Gersunsky, A.P. Tryapitsina, V.A. Slastonin, E.A. Klimov, A.B. Khutorskoy, A.K. Markova, V.A. Adolf, E.K. Rakitin, V.V. Yevdokimov, V.P. Kosarev, P.V. Koshokhovskiy, A.M. Novikov, V.A. The research and research of world scientists like Shapalov can be a clear proof of this.

If you look at the history of pedagogy, you can see that the competency-based approach is widespread in Western Europe and the United States. As noted in the documents of the Council of Europe, the most important feature of modern education is that it is aimed at actively mastering the state of social changes, using the set of basic competencies as a basis. It should be noted that the set of competencies is mainly the following: cognitive, social, informational, etc. Among this complex, the concepts of information competence or having information competence are very characteristic of the current educational period. Because, as mentioned above, the credit-module system in higher education institutions requires this involuntarily.

After all, the credit-module system, which is available in the educational institutions of the state and has been systematically used for the last 3-5 years, has strengthened the requirements for students to have information competence. The reason is that both the announcement of lesson processes organized in higher education institutions, monitoring and evaluation of students' knowledge, and any kind of cultural and educational events organized by higher education institutions are covered on the basis of the credit-module system. That is, the personal profile of the student body is published on the existing systematic platform.

The increasing role of information in the life of society and the use of information technologies in various areas of professional activity allow to define information competence as the main one. The problem of developing the information competence of future specialists is becoming more and more urgent in the modern information society, which is saturated with the means of storing, processing and transmitting information based on new information technologies [1].

According to A.B. Khutorskoy, O.G. Smolyaninova, A.M. Orobinsky, A.Yu. Orshansky, M.M. Pshukova, A.B. Vishnyakova, O.B. Zaitseva, O.M. Chubaryan and other world scientists, information competence implies free direction in information flows: from computers, telecommunications and other means of communication. independent reception, processing and use of information by the subject; he (the subject) must have the ability to use information technologies to solve the problems he has set to achieve the goal of his activity. At the same time, it should not be forgotten that computers and programs are the tools on which information technology relies. In addition to the formation of the ability to freely manage information flows, information competence implies fluency in non-verbal communication with other people using modern IT tools.

The activity of specialists increasingly depends on their possession of certain information and the ability to use this information effectively. A modern specialist in any field must know how

to receive, process and use information with the help of computers, telecommunications and other means of information technology in order to move freely in the information flow. The need for qualified specialists who have mastered the society's arsenal (set) of informatics tools and methods is becoming a leading factor and concept of education policy. In order to improve the credit-module system in higher education institutions and to further improve the concept of information competence of students, who are the main participants of education, from the current state, it is related to the organizational, material-technical, scientific-methodical aspects of the development and implementation of modern information technologies. despite the certain level of difficulties associated with them, they are attracting a certain level of interest in a number of field experts. Because here, like in other fields, it is primarily necessary to effectively collect, process and transfer information from traditional forms of training aimed at gathering a certain level of knowledge, skills and abilities, independent work and education. there is a need to switch to information and communication technologies that allow qualitative changes in the content, methods and organizational forms of education.

In short, in the professional training of future teachers, the introduction of new forms and methods into the traditional education system, the introduction of certain changes, which are reflected both in the teacher's activity and in the student's activity. The development of the education system should be carried out based on the following priorities:

qualitatively updating the content of the educational system in various directions, as well as training qualified professional pedagogic personnel, teaching creative teachers in the relevant areas of higher education institutions, pedagogy, didactics, practical pedagogical psychology, methodology, general professional and improvement of the teacher training system through the development of educational materials and pedagogical evaluation, with a special focus on special subjects;

increase the level of computerization in the higher education system, regardless of the direction, taking into account the modern trends of the development of information and communication technologies;

issues of organizing the preparation and printing of new generation textbooks and teaching-methodical literature using information and communication technologies are the basis for the development of information-communicative and professional competence of pedagogues in the environment of modern information technologies.

REFERENCES

1. Dilshoda Jalilova. BOSHLANG I C H TA'LIM O'QITUVCHILARINING KASBIY KOMPETENSIYASI TARKIBIY QISMLARINING MAZMUN-MOHIYATI. «O'ZBEKISTONDAILM-FANNINGRIVOJLANISHISTIOLLARI" xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjumani 2022-yil 30-noyabr. 839-842-betlar. (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377842>)
2. Dilshoda Jalilova Ural qizi. BO'LAJAK BOSHLANG'ICH SINIF O'QITUVCHILARIDA AXBOROT KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MASALASINING AHAMIYATI. RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR DAVRIDA TILLARNI INTENSIV O'QITISHNING PSIXOLOGIK- PEDAGOGIK JIHATLARI RESPUBLIKA ILMIY-AMALIY ANJUMANI. 2023-yil 2-iyun (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7993607>) .

3. Jalilova D. Ta'lim jarayonlarining samaradorligini oshirish uchun innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanishning ahamiyati. "Sifatli ta'lim - taraqqiyot povdevori" mavzusidagi Respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya to'plami // Toshkent, 2023-yil 20-aprel. 282-286-betlar.
4. Yakibova Dilorom Sharifovna. DEVELOPMENT OF TECHNOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 3 ISSUE 3 MARCH 2024. 348-351p.
5. Nuradilova Aselxan Dilshodxo'ja qizi. Boshlang'ich sinflarda ona tili fanini o'qitishda noan'anaviy dars usulining samarali natijalari. МУҒАЛЛИМ ҲӘМ ҮЗЛИКСИЗ БИЛИМЛЕНДИРИЎ. Tom1. 241-246b.
6. Raven J. Zamonaviy jamiyatda kompetensiya: aniqlash, ishlab chiqish va amalga oshirish / Tarjima. ingliz tilidan M., "Cogito-Markaz", 2002. - 396 b.